

Influence of weeds and rice cultivar on nematode population densities in lowland rice

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Weed competition is a major constraint to rice production in the hydromorphic/flood-prone ecosystem because moist conditions encourage rapid weed growth and permit rapid reestablishment of disturbed weeds. Rice root nematodes *Hirschmanniella* spp. and *Tylenchorhynchus* spp. are cosmopolitan in these rice production systems and are associated with economic losses. Current recommendations for their management are limited.

The African rice *Oryza glaberrima* provides a rich source of resistance to numerous biotic stresses and tolerance for unfavorable abiotic stresses in West Africa. Recent advances in crop improvement at WARDA have produced interspecific progeny of *O. glaberrima* and *O. sativa*, that combine the useful traits of both parents.

Experiments were designed to assess the performance of a range of plant types, including *O. glaberrima* and *O. sativa* parents, and progeny, in hydromorphic/flood-prone rice. These plant types were assessed for their susceptibility to parasitic nematodes in 1996 and repeated in 1997.

Rice was dry-seeded into a clean seedbed using five seeds hill⁻¹ spaced 25 cm apart, in 4 × 5-m plots. A randomized block design was used with four replications. The two factors studied were cultivars (seven) (see table) and weed management at two levels: weed-free (preemergence herbicide and subsequent hand-weeding) and with weeds (weeds uncontrolled from 14 d after rice emergence [DAE]). Each replicate included a weed-only control plot. Fertilizer was applied as 20 kg P ha⁻¹ at sowing and 46 kg N ha⁻¹ in equal splits at 28 and 56 DAE. Nematode population densities were estimated at 90 DAE from 100-mL soil and 5-g root subsamples from five hills plot⁻¹, which

were incubated for 48 h using a modified Baermann technique. At sowing, single-core samples from each plot were bulked by replicates and the presence of nematodes established from 100-mL subsamples.

Major weed species present were *Fimbristylis littoralis*, *Cyperus difformis*, *C. esculentus*, *Sphenoclea zeylanica*, *Echinochloa crus-gavonis*, *E. colona*, *Spilanthus uliginosa*, and *Bacopa decumbens*. *Hirschmanniella oryzae* and *T. annulatus* were present at sowing in all replications in each experiment. Neither cultivar nor weed management influenced *T. annulatus* population densities. *H. oryzae* population density was consistently influenced by cultivar. In both experiments, some progeny supported greater ($P < 0.001$) population densities of *H. oryzae* than the parents and appeared to

be highly susceptible to the nematode. Weed management influenced population density of *H. oryzae* in the first but not in the second experiment. The presence of weeds in rice, and weeds alone, resulted in suppressed *H. oryzae* populations. *E. colona*, *Echinochloa* spp., *Cyperus* spp. (Mohandas et al 1979, Koreyem 1993), and *Fimbristylis* spp. have previously been found to be good hosts of *H. oryzae*, and *S. zeylanica* (Mohandas et al 1979), a nonhost. No rice cultivar was resistant to either nematode.

Two main conclusions can be drawn from this study. First, some of the new interspecific progeny appear to be highly susceptible to *H. oryzae*. Second, improvements in weed control may raise the pest status of *H. oryzae*, in hydromorphic/flooded rice. With escalating local demand for rice, intensification of production is

Nematode population densities of *Hirschmanniella oryzae* and *Tylenchorhynchus annulatus* on *Oryza sativa* and *O. glaberrima* parents, and interspecific hybrids, under two weed management conditions in lowland rice at 90 DAS; plants spaced 25 cm apart.

Cultivar	Varietal type	1996		1997	
		<i>H. oryzae</i>	<i>T. annulatus</i>	<i>H. oryzae</i>	<i>T. annulatus</i>
Bouaké 189	<i>O. sativa</i>	609	240	415	127
CG14	<i>O. glaberrima</i>	433	170	402	88
WAB450-24-3-2P18-HB	Progeny	407	167	353	105
WAB450-1-BP-26-1-1	Progeny	781	290	335	151
WAB450-1-BP-133-HB	Progeny	956	236	1441	103
WAB450-1-BP-106-HB	Progeny	1627	208	1464	95
WAB450-11-1-P40-1-HB	Progeny	874	263	840	93
Weeds only (control)		690	202	142	63
LSD ($P < 0.05$)		428	-	111	-
<i>P</i>		<0.000	ns ^a	<0.000	ns
<i>Weed management</i>					
Weed-free		987	247	757	119
Weeds after 14 DAE		638	203	744	98
<i>P</i>		0.004	ns	ns	ns

^ans = not significant.

occurring. Part of this intensification process will involve improved weed management, yet it is important that such changes do not favor the development of pest nematodes.

References

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Multilocational screening of *Oryza sativa* and *O. glaberrima* for resistance to African rice gall midge *Orseolia oryzivora* in West Africa

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Resistance to the Asian rice gall midge *Orseolia oryzae* differs markedly from one location to another because of the existence of genetically distinct biotypes of the pest with differing abilities to overcome resistance genes in their host. To investigate whether the same phenomenon occurs in the African rice gall midge (AfRGM), *Orseolia oryzivora*, the WARDA Integrated Pest Management (IPM) Task Force undertook multilocational screening of *Oryza sativa* and *O. glaberrima* varieties during the wet season at six locations in 1996 and at four sites in 1997. Trial sites were Ogidiga and Gadza in southeast and central Nigeria, respectively; Karfiguéla and Banzon, both in southwest Burkina Faso; Longorola, in south Mali; and Rokupr, in west Sierra Leone.

Rice seed was supplied by Dr. N.Q. Ng of the International Institute of Tropical Agriculture and Dr. B.N. Singh of WARDA. The *sativas* used were a highly susceptible check (ITA306) and African and Asian varieties which, from previous screening in Nigeria, showed significantly lower infestation than ITA306, although most were at least moderately susceptible to rice gall midge. The *glaberrimas* used were all highly to moderately resistant in an earlier screening in Nigeria. Trials were randomized complete block designs with three blocks in which *sativas* and *glaberrimas* were randomized together.

They were carried out in rainfed lowland or irrigated conditions depending on location. Each plot had two rows of 15 hills each, transplanted at 20 × 20 cm with two seedlings hill⁻¹ at 21 d after sowing (DAS). Basal fertilizer application was 40 kg N, P, and K ha⁻¹. A topdressing of 40 kg N ha⁻¹ was applied at 20 d after transplanting

(DAT). AfRGM tiller infestation levels were calculated from gall and tiller counts on 20 hills plot⁻¹ at 63 DAT.

Results showed that AfRGM pressure was high at all locations except Longorola, Mali (Tables 1 and 2). In both years, location had a large effect on AfRGM infestation level on many test entries rela-

Table 1. Percentage of tillers with AfRGM galls at 63 DAT (mean + standard error) at six trial locations, 1996.

Entry ^a	Ogidiga, southeast Nigeria	Gadza, central Nigeria	Karfiguéla, Burkina Faso	Banzon, Burkina Faso	Longorola, Mali	Rokupr, Sierra Leone
<i>sativas</i>						
ITA306 (check)	36.7 + 5.22	27.5 + 3.84	26.9 + 3.67	21.8 + 3.57	6.2 + 0.28	28.2 + 3.05
TOS8144	26.2 + 0.93	9.9 + 2.56	17.1 + 3.04	20.3 + 1.76	5.3 + 1.40	11.8 + 1.32
Eguazankpa	28.7 + 1.14	4.7 + 1.73	21.0 + 2.65	22.2 + 1.68	1.5 + 0.35	3.5 + 0.92
ARC 6618	20.2 + 4.32	8.5 + 2.49	14.5 + 2.12	16.1 + 1.38	3.2 + 0.52	4.8 + 1.27
Nhta 8	18.9 + 4.39	8.9 + 3.96	5.3 + 1.33	12.5 + 1.29	8.2 + 2.27	2.9 + 0.84
Aganni	22.8 + 4.77	5.8 + 1.40	4.4 + 0.52	13.0 + 0.51	2.4 + 1.35	2.4 + 0.66
All <i>sativas</i>	25.6	10.9	14.9	17.7	4.5	8.9
<i>glaberrimas</i>						
TOG7684	0.3 + 0.27	9.1 + 1.23	8.8 + 0.59	12.1 + 1.26	6.7 + 2.53	0.0 + 0.00
TOG6542	1.2 + 1.01	3.3 + 0.98	9.4 + 1.15	13.2 + 2.60	9.5 + 4.53	0.0 + 0.00
TOG6631	0.0 + 0.00	3.7 + 0.53	14.0 + 2.87	12.4 + 1.75	4.3 + 1.23	0.0 + 0.00
TOG6582	0.4 + 0.21	2.8 + 1.04	8.9 + 1.33	14.6 + 5.69	7.2 + 3.09	0.0 + 0.00
TOG7442	0.0 + 0.00	5.3 + 3.65	10.7 + 1.24	6.9 + 1.85	9.6 + 4.00	0.0 + 0.00
TOG7677	0.0 + 0.00	3.8 + 2.08	14.2 + 3.05	7.2 + 0.72	4.7 + 1.26	0.0 + 0.00
TOG6589	0.3 + 0.28	3.1 + 0.57	6.7 + 1.13	11.3 + 1.08	6.5 + 2.94	0.0 + 0.00
TOG6508	0.0 + 0.00	2.7 + 0.89	8.7 + 0.48	11.7 + 1.29	3.7 + 2.43	0.0 + 0.00
TOG7198	0.0 + 0.00	2.3 + 0.54	6.3 + 1.03	11.1 + 1.09	5.7 + 2.41	0.0 + 0.00
TOG6216	0.3 + 0.30	3.2 + 2.00	5.6 + 2.67	4.3 + 2.75	6.0 + 2.50	0.0 + 0.00
All <i>glaberrimas</i>	0.3	3.9	9.3	10.5	6.4	0.0

^a*sativas* and *glaberrimas* are listed in the order of mean infestation level across all sites.